

KHODJEYLI IN HISTORICAL NOTES

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Аннотация: В этой статье рассматриваются экономические и социальные аспекты района Ходжейли в XVII и XX веках, задокументированные русскими исследователями, военными и учеными в их журналах, статьях и трудах.

Ключевые слова: Каракалпаки, Ходжейли, Амударья, Аральское море, Российская империя, Хивинское ханство

Annotation: This article examines the economic and social aspects of the Khodjeyli district during the 17th and 20th centuries, as documented by Russian explorers, military personnel, and scholars in their journals, articles, and writings.

Keywords: Karakalpaks, Khodjeyli, Amudarya, Aral Sea, Russian Empire, Khiva Khanate

Khodjeyli is considered one of the five historic cities famous among the Karakalpaks. Scientific evidence indicates that this area has been inhabited for over 2,400 years. The city has had various names, including Gaur, Antakiya, and Mizdakhan, before it became known as Khodjeyli. The Silk Road passed through this region, facilitating cultural exchange and trade between the East and West. According to the 10th-century Arab geographer Mahdisi, Mizdakhan was one of the earliest cities in the area. References to Mizdakhan can also be found in the works of his contemporaries Abu Ali ibn Umar and Ibn Ruste al Istakhri. Records from Russian and other foreign travelers, explorers, and members of military expeditions provide insight into the old markets of the region, irrigation systems, and the economy of its inhabitants [1].

The works, diaries, memory records, and articles created by state employees, ambassadors, travelers, and scientists of the Russian Empire are extremely valuable in studying the history of the Karakalpak people from the XVII-XX centuries. These sources provide historical information and offer valuable insights into the nature, living conditions, cities, and economy of the Karakalpak inhabited territory, including the Khodjeyli district.

Gladishev and Muravin provide information on the 18th-century coasts of Syrdarya and the Aral Sea, as well as the cities of Khiva, Shakhtemir, Khodjeyli,

Kungrad, Khanqah, and Shovot in the Khiva Khanate, and the Karakalpak, Kazakh, and Uzbek peoples [2].

In the summer of 1873, after the Russian Empire had conquered the Khanate of Khiva, A. Kun, M. N. Bogdanov, and I. Krauze arrived in Khiva to study the living peoples of the Khanate, their culture, cities, trade routes, and other geographical information. They first arrived in Khodjeyli after traveling through Khiva, Gazavat, Tashauz, and Kohna Urgench.

In his article, A. Kuhn provides detailed accounts of the people who reside in the Amudarya Oasis, their way of life, and the cities they inhabit. The article notes that the city of Khodjeyli boasts the largest central market for the Karakalpak people on the Right Bank of the Amudarya. The market was the hub for trading cotton, fish, and other products that were imported from other cities. He stated that Khodjeyli was founded in the 12th century. It is possible to travel from Khodjeyli to Kungrad in one day by water or two days by land. Every year, between 50 to 200 boats filled with shellfish were sent from Khodjeyli and Kungrad to be sold in Bukhara, Samarkand, Karshi, and Shakhrisabz [3]. In the 1870s, the city of Khodjeyli was situated on both sides of the Suenli Canal. It was known for its abundance of marinas, with shops built on either side of the canal. Fishing was also a thriving industry in the city, and its inhabitants enjoyed a prosperous way of life [4].

Bogdanov, a member of the Amudarya expedition, studied the fauna, birds, and fish of the lower Amudarya [5]. He provided information about the watersheds in the area and the various species of fish found there, as well as the fishing centers and the weapons used for fishing. In the second half of the 19th century, the following fishing centers were identified:

1. Along both banks of the Amudarya, from Nukus and Khodjeyli upwards to Kipchak, where Suwen, Ilaqa, Sazan, and other fish were caught.
2. From Nukus to the Aral Sea, and in the Aral Sea itself, where Bekire, Suwen, Ilaqa, Sazan, and other fish were caught.
3. Lake Kungrad and Qarateren, where Sazan and Aqmarqa were commonly found.

In his work, Danilevsky provided information about the Khanate of Khiva, the peoples of Ustyurt, and the Aral Sea [6]. He discussed the socio-economic life of the cities of Chimbay, Khodjeyli, and Kungrad, which were considered the administrative center. Chimbay had a large caravan palace and 150 shops, while Kungrad had 350 shops and Khodjeyli had 150 shops. These cities played a crucial role in domestic trade.

Nikolay Nikolaevich Karazin (1842-1908) was a Russian writer and painter who was also part of the Amudarya expedition under Stoletov in 1874. He is known for his paintings depicting the way of life and the stunning nature of the Karakalpak people. In 1874, N.N. Karazin visited Khodjeyli and was amazed by its excellent natural beauty and high economic activity, describing it as the «Venice on the Amudarya». A picture of this place was published in the magazine «Niva» in 1886.

In 1888, Kaulbars issued "Atlas maps of the Amudarya Delta" in Russia. These maps show the arrangement of Karakalpaks in fortified towns, cemeteries, pilgrimage sites, and settlements. The Atlas Cards include the formations of cities like Shah Abbas, Khodjeyli, Chimbay, and Kungrad.

Alexander Nikolaevich Samoylovich (1880-1938) purchased a saga about Genghis Khan's conquest of Khwarezm at the 1908 Khodjeyli Bazaar. He also bought a book on the life of Najmiddin Kubro, the epic "Khorezmnoma". During this time, the knives of Khodjeyli were highly regarded for their quality and design. A.N. Samoylovich also bought two of these knives. He then used his own camera to take pictures of the Nazlumkhonsuluv mausoleum and Gaur fortress [7].

Before and after the Russian Empire conquered the Khanate of Khiva, there was an interest in exploring the lands around the Delta of the Amudarya River and the Aral Sea. To achieve this, several expeditions were organized, which provided valuable information about the territory of Karakalpakstan.

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